

Asociația Școala de Valori / The School of Values

**The School of Values: The Democratic
School**

Translation in English of the article published in Romanian

iCercetare / iResearch

This publication is intended for primary school teachers, secondary school teachers, and pre-service teachers working in Romania's pre-university education system. It may also be of interest to trainers active in other learning or educational environments.

The iCercetare initiative addresses the need to understand learning and education beyond the content being taught (Romanian language, mathematics, geography, etc.), focusing instead on the interactions and activities through which the actors involved in learning “shape and transform its culture, values, practices, and other specific characteristics” (Ilomäki & Lakkala 2018, p. 2).

This publication is based on data collected by The School of Values within the “Digital Civic Incubator” (ICD) project—a digital citizenship program created and implemented by a consortium of three NGOs: The School of Values, the Intercultural Institute of Timișoara, and Techsoup Association, with the support of the Ministry of Education. The project is funded by Fondation Botnar and aims to develop competencies related to integrating digital technologies into teaching practice, implementing democratic leadership and decision-making processes, and promoting active citizenship and intercultural dialogue.

The article “The Democratic School” documents and analyzes practices that emerged through the interaction with teachers participating in ICD training activities: practices of connecting, practices of response, observation practices, and practices of (re)recognizing the students' needs.

The results of this exploratory analysis were presented to ICD project participants during community meetings, where they provided feedback as well as examples of classroom activities, which we include in the section “Activities Implemented by Teachers in the ICD Community.” Recognizing teachers not only as subjects, but also as partners and co-authors in the ICD learning and research process naturally supported the transfer of these practices into classroom settings.

ABSTRACT

The publication „The School of Values: the Democratic School” aligns with existing efforts to promote democratic culture and civic citizenship in schools in Romania. The article proposes a „whole school approach”, based on interaction and democratic values. The qualitative analysis highlights pedagogical practices and practices of the teaching community, namely connection practices, feedback practices, observation practices and practices of (re)cognition of students' needs, contributing to a better understanding of the affordances of the democratic, innovative and digital school.

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Learning as a social process, situated in a community of practice

Illomäki and Lakkala published the model of the innovative and digital school in 2018 (2018, p. 10). For the authors, the school is “is an environment of collaborative, social activities of teachers, pupils and other participants; and their activities shape and transform its culture, values, practices and other specific characteristics (Illomäki & Lakkala 2018, p. 2)”.

By examining studies that used a variety of research approaches, Illomäki and Lakkala proposed a model of the innovative and digital school (2018, p. 10), which includes the following elements: the vision of the school, leadership, teaching community practices, pedagogical practices, school-level knowledge practices, and digital resources. The first three elements concern teachers and school leaders, while the last three involve teachers, school leaders, and students.

Like Illomäki and Lakkala, we adopt a sociocultural perspective on learning: learning is co-constructed through interaction with the resources available in the learning environment at any given moment. Practices are the interactional routines (Ziegler 2011, p. 10) within these co-constructed moments, and learning is “a social process, situated in communities of practice” (Brouwer & Wagner 2004, p. 32).

By adding the dimension of the democratic school, Silvia Bogdan adapted the model proposed by Illomäki and Lakkala (2018) into Romanian, thus proposing a model of the democratic, innovative, and digital school (Fig. 1). This democratic school dimension is the focus of the present exploratory analysis.

The model presented in Fig. 1 proposes identifying the extent to which the principles of democracy and human rights are integrated into school life, by examining the resources, challenges, strengths, and weaknesses of leadership, and by considering the participation of all stakeholders at multiple levels: (macro) the school and school-level leadership; (meso) the teaching community; and (micro) the classroom, teacher–student interaction, and student–student interaction. The model responds to the need to redefine the concept of the “didactic contract.” The term “didactic contract”, introduced in language sciences by De Pietro, Matthey, and Py (1988), was first applied in mathematics education by G. Brousseau, who defined it as “the (specific) habits [practices] of the teacher expected by the student, and the behaviors of the student expected by the teacher” (De Pietro, Matthey & Py 1988, p. 99, citing Brousseau, 1980, p. 181, our translation, 1).

The definition provided by Moore and Simon in 2002 adds an important element to the didactic contract: the vertical distribution of knowledge:

„The didactic contract that binds the teacher and the learner is institutionalized; it establishes certain rights and obligations and positions the actors along an expert–non-expert axis. This is based primarily on a vertical distribution of knowledge, which determines who is expected to speak and who controls the discourse” (Moore și Simon 2002, p. 2, our translation, 2).

1. Ces habitudes (spécifiques) du maître attendues par l'élève et ces comportements de l'élève attendus par le maître (De Pietro, Matthey et Py 1988, p. 99 citând Brousseau, 1980, p. 181).

2. Le contrat didactique qui lie l'enseignant et l'apprenant est institutionnalisé, il fixe certains droits et des obligations, et positionne les acteurs sur un axe expert-non-expert, selon une distribution surtout verticale du savoir, qui ordonne l'orientation des prises de parole et le contrôle du discours (Moore et Simon 2002, p. 2).

The Model of the Democratic, Innovative and Digital school

Fig. 1, Model adapted by Silvia Bogdan, after “The model of digital innovative school” (Ilomäki & Lakkala 2018)

Through the “democratic school” model (Ilomäki & Lakkala 2018, adapted by Silvia Bogdan), the transition is facilitated from a vertical model to a more horizontal, collaborative one, in which the didactic contract supports the creation of an “extended learning territory” (Py 2000, p. 2) for the student.

In the transition toward a horizontal model, teachers and students need knowledge and critical understanding of both themselves and the school/environment in which they are active. In the right context, participating teachers or students discover how to leverage individual potential for the benefit of the class/school (in the broader sense). Referring symbolically to the question that inspired the creation of the Rubik’s cube, they discover how we can function individually/independently while at the same time aligning with the movements of others. When alignment does not occur, we can speak of “contradictions” (Kramsch 1993, p. 75), practices of a contradictory and subversive nature, in which students’ perceptions of the activity and the teacher’s expectations fail to meet.

Practices of the teaching community and pedagogical practices for a democratic school

The model of the democratic, innovative, and digital school (Fig. 1) is a “whole-school approach” model, a form of democratic culture applied at the level of the entire school. It is a concept highlighted by the Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture (Council of Europe 2018) and defined as follows:

„Competences for democratic culture are important for learners, but also for schools as an institution and for the community as a whole. If they are to participate effectively in a culture of democracy and live peacefully together with others in culturally diverse democratic societies, citizens need to be able to recognise and practise democratic principles. (...) A whole-school approach to CDC ensures that all aspects of school life – curricula, teaching methods and resources, leadership and decision-making structures and processes, policies and codes of behaviour, staff and staff–student relationships, extracurricular activities and links with the community – reflect democratic and human rights principles. In turn, this may create a safe learning environment where these principles can be explored, experienced and even challenged in a peaceful way.” (Council of Europe 2018, vol. 3, p. 90-91).

In what follows, we focus on two elements from the adapted model of the democratic, innovative, and digital school: pedagogical practices (connecting practices, observation practices, response practices) and practices of the teaching community (connecting practices, observation practices, practices of recognizing/acknowledging needs).

Connecting practices

Roser highlights the importance of energizing activities or games beyond the usual 2–3 minutes of physical break, emphasizing the importance of building a teacher–student or teacher–teacher connection from a democratic school perspective:

„We need to find a way to develop deeper relationships with our students, for as studies show, those students who have positive connections with their teachers experience the most success in school and in life. In addition to addressing the brain's need for physical breaks and exercise, play between teachers and students creates a bond that allows both to experience each other in a natural, friendly way. It's an opportunity for students to see another side of their teacher” (Roser, 2015).

This connection is further strengthened in energizing activities that involve physical contact, as we observed on several occasions during the ICD congress (Figs. 2 and 3):

Fig. 2 Representation of an energizer

Fig. 3 Energizer with a group of teachers participating in the ICD congress, July 2024

The introduction of energizing exercises involves a pedagogy of “interactive modeling” (Roser 2015, p. iv): naming the model, describing it, demonstrating it as a teacher (“watch me do it now”), gathering students’ observations, having students demonstrate it, gathering their observations again, performing the model with the whole group, and providing feedback.

Energizer moments therefore go beyond their initial function as breaks, play, or focus activities and become moments in which students learn to observe, develop their motor skills, and connect with the teacher/trainer and with their peers. Through their connecting function, energizer moments contribute to community building, an important objective of the democratic school, as mentioned by the Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture:

„all school subjects can make good use of short icebreakers, grouping techniques and other team-building and evaluation activities to ensure that the classroom becomes a supportive community of learners who are increasingly motivated to learn together and contribute, and who trust each other and wish to co-operate.” (Council of Europe 2018, vol. 3, p. 38-39).

The framework encourages the use of the existing curriculum for activities that contribute to a democratic culture, rather than isolated and unintegrated activities which „can have the negative consequence of an inevitable superficiality that both obscures and scatters the fundamentally important messages” (Council of Europe 2018, p. 41).

Suggested classroom activities: energizers

Whole class. Students stand up, forming one (or several) circles. The energizer from Figs. 2 and 3 is performed: the right index finger rests on the palm of the person on the right, while the left palm is placed over the index finger of the person on the left. The instructions are given: the teacher narrates some content (from any subject), and each time something incorrect is said, the student must pull back their index finger to avoid being caught by the partner on the right, while at the same time trying to catch the index finger of the partner on the left with their left palm. The steps of the “interactive modeling” pedagogy (Roser 2015, p. iv) described above are followed.

Observation practices

In the transition from the vertical model (where the teacher holds the information and the decision-making power) to the horizontal model which integrates democratic behaviors, the student can act from the position of expert.

During some activities carried out at the ICD Congress, two participants (teachers) were invited to be “observers” with the instruction to note anything they considered relevant. Below (Example 1) we reproduce part of the discussion in which Observer 3 reported their observations. The observers took on this role voluntarily; they were not appointed.

Example 1_ICD_2024

```
012  Obs3:  au existat niște momente în care era mai  
      there were some moments when there was  
013      puțină atenție (...) au fost prea multe  
      less attention (...) there were too many  
014      exemple alese (.) poate mai puține  
      examples used (.) maybe fewer
```

Observer 3 focused on the group’s reactions, noting in line 12 that “there were some moments when there was less attention,” followed by identification of the problematic point (lines 13-14), “there were too many examples used,” and a suggestion addressed to the trainer, “maybe fewer [examples].”

On the day following this activity, a teacher asked the trainer a follow-up question at breakfast, in an informal setting: “How do we stay calm when the activity we designed is being criticized?”

A first idea highlights the importance of this informal setting, which allows such questions to be asked, and from here, the importance of the hors-cadre (outside the usual frame) and hors-jeu (beyond established, habitual interactions) context provided by the ICD congress: we are not in a school, not in a meeting, etc.; we are in a learning space where we can ask any question.

The second idea that emerged unfolds into two questions: How do we accept others’ observations when they go beyond description into identifying a possible conflict of opinion and then into stating a problematic point (lines 12-14)? How do we know how to be vulnerable (Brown 2016) when we are in the position of trainer/expert/classroom teacher, in order to broaden the learning territory toward increasing students’ control over discourse and interaction in the classroom?

Moore and Simon speak of the “deritualization of learning scenarios constructed by teachers” (Moore & Simon 2002, p. 9) in favor of the student. Three aspects of this deritualization are particularly useful: positioning, spontaneity, and control. Positioning refers to the difficulty students experience in “managing discourse and guiding classroom discourse” (Moore & Simon 2002, p. 8). With regard to spontaneity, we observe that “spontaneous negotiations are few in number in the classroom” (Moore & Simon 2002, p. 8, citing Toohey 2000). As for control, “in general, students have little control over classroom discourse” (Moore & Simon 2002, p. 8).

Changing the didactic contract and expanding the student's learning territory contribute to the co-construction of the democratic school. By a change of frame, we understand both a change in positioning (participants positioned themselves as experts when presenting their observations) and a change of environment to foster spontaneity (at the ICD congress, participants were able to interact in a broader setting than the school where they work), as well as the creation of a space for vulnerability, which offers participants more control. This space of vulnerability also involves looking at failure—at what did not work. Brené Brown notes that “Failure is not learning gone bad, it is not the opposite of learning. Failure is part of the learning process” (Brown 2016, p. 4). Brown encourages us to ask the following questions:

„What did you learn about yourself in the process of preparing, taking, and receiving this exam? What is the learning here for you? What would you do differently? What would you do the same? What do you know about yourself that you didn't know before you took the exam? These conversations are about not just the product of our learning but the process of our learning. To me, these can be so powerful. It takes time, and it takes someone who believes in the transformative power of the classroom” (Brown 2016, p. 4).

Vulnerability is not always associated with feelings of “loneliness” or “alienation” (Council of Europe 2018, p. 106); it can also be understood as the beginning of a learning and development process. One participant at the ICD Congress mentioned at the end of her presentation: “I don't know if I expressed myself correctly or if you understood me.” This participant has a plurilingual repertoire that includes linguistic resources beyond Romanian. Figures 4 and 5 show how she opens her palms and looks around the circle of participants, inviting them to contribute to the discussion from this position of vulnerability.

Fig. 4 Representation of a discussion circle

Fig. 5 Discussion circle, ICD Congress, July 2024

Suggested classroom activities: observing the interaction

The teachers participating in the ICD congress were encouraged to become observers of classroom interaction by: (i) observing a colleague's lesson, or (ii) video/audio recording a lesson they themselves were teaching. We provided the teachers with an observation sheet for a classroom activity, an adaptation in Romanian after Artzt, A. & Armour-Thomas, E. (2002, p. 135).

Response practices

Often in the classroom, students offer answers that are not validated by the teacher as correct and that are sometimes treated as a “joking event” (Cekaite and Aronsson 2004, p. 376), an event some students find amusing. Ziegler et al. (2015) show that this type of phenomenon is quite widespread, as we see in Example 2 below, taken from the first day of the ICD Congress.

The phenomenon involves using a provisional form as a response to a question; these provisional terms are then replaced with definitive terms, which are validated by the participants (Krafft and Dausendschön-Gay 1999, p. 64).

Exemplul 2_ICD_2024

001 For1: sunteți de acord cu propunerea asta?
do you agree with this idea?

002 Toți: da::
yes

003 For1: bine. <<dictează pentru For2 care scrie pe
okay. <<dictates for the colleague who writes
004 un poster>deci colectarea petului
on a poster> so collecting plastic bottles
005 For2: și mâncat sustenabil,>
and eating sustainably>

006 For1: colectare de pet-uri și::: ce ai zis,
plastic recycling and what have you said

007 For1: și: papa ș:=papa sustenabil
and sustainable food

008 Toți: <<participanții râd> ha=ha>
<<participants laugh> ha=ha>

009 For2: doamnele profesoare de limba română (.)
teachers of romanian language
010 o exprimare în limba română despre
how do we say this in Romanian please
011 papa sustenabil
sustainable food

012 Parl: fără risipă.
without waste

Fig. 6 Representation of frontal interaction

In Example 2, the two trainers write the group rules on a poster, rules previously discussed with the whole group. Trainer 1 dictates to Trainer 2 the idea that was originally discussed with the group (lines 3-4), “collecting plastic bottles and eating sustainably.” Trainer 2 asks them to repeat the second element in lines 5 and 6. Trainer 1 searches for the term with eyes closed and, hesitating, verbalizes “sustainable food,” which amuses the participants. This response is not accepted by Trainer 2, who asks the group for help with a reformulation (lines 8-10). A participant offers another response, “without waste,” which becomes the term that is written down. Ziegler et al. (2015) note that provisional terms are extremely important because they help the sequence continue, filling in for the definitive term that will later be fixed in writing.

A resource initially perceived as a problem/error is then reframed as a resource that contributes to the interaction, thus supporting the valorization of students’ diverse competences. At the level of the adjacency pair, the “relation of adjacency or contiguity” (Schegloff 2007, p. 14) does not discourage the speaker’s future participation—without this implying that we validate an incorrect answer in every situation. At the opposite extreme is teacher feedback consisting of “no” or “incorrect,” along with practices in which students laugh when a classmate gives an incorrect answer or needs more time to produce one, ultimately leading to that student’s marginalization.

Suggested classroom activities: word game/invented words

Without intending to promote incorrect language forms, students can be invited to explore the lyrics of the band Phoenix (written by Șerban Foarță and Andrei Ujică) or other poems by Șerban Foarță in order to investigate the meaning and form of words they have not encountered before. In poetry—as in conversation—rhythm and rhyme play an important role, with words often occurring in a particular sequential order as Sacks confesses: „There might be a family of relationships; sometimes semantic, other times sound” (Sacks 1992, 2, p. 292-293). Within the question-answer sequence, Tannen (2007) emphasizes that „The pattern of repeated and varied sounds, words, phrases, sentences and longer discourse sequences gives the impression, indeed the reality, of a shared universe of discourse” (Tannen 2007, p. 62).

Practices of recognition of students' needs

In his 2000 article “Toward a Theory of Anti-oppressive Education”, Kevin Kumashiro reframes the pronoun “Other”—understood as “Those groups that are traditionally marginalized in society” (Kumashiro 2000, p. 26)—into the participle “Othered” when he proposes “improving the experiences of students who are Othered, or in some way oppressed, in and by mainstream society” (Kumashiro 2000, p. 26).

In the legacy of Foucault, Lindin and Torpsten argue that “education is a system that maintains or changes the discourses, thus maintaining knowledge and power” (2018, p. 577).

The discourse we use with and about our students is a space for reflection and learning and, when needed, for change.

We focus here on a discourse constructed during an exercise dedicated to strengthening resilience to change in the ICD Congress week. Teachers were invited to propose ways to come closer to the students they work with, starting from several challenging situations they were given:

1. Students with social anxiety.
2. Students experiencing bullying.
3. Students with learning difficulties.
4. Students going through major life changes (e.g., parents' divorce, moving to a new city).

Each group of teachers was encouraged to develop three components:

1. A detailed description of the situation.
2. Specific techniques and strategies to help the student develop resilience.
3. An implementation plan and a system for monitoring progress.

Below, we present the work of the group that developed the topic “Students with Social Anxiety.” We selected this discourse based on the trainers' invitation to reflect, as a larger group, on this example.

Exemplul 3_ICD_2024

001 P1: și am zis ca prin rotație, în fiecare modul
I said that on a rotation basis in each module
002 să stea o altă domnișoară
a different girl should sit with him
003 cu el în bancă. ca și proiect de grup ne-am gândit
at the desk. as a group project we thought about
004 să organizăm o excursie și elevul cu anxietate
organizing a trip and the student with social anxiety
005 să fie cel care propune
would be the one to suggest
006 care sunt obiectivele turistice de vizitat. (...)
which toursit attractions we should visit
007 P2: eu nu l-aș pune doar pe el (.) eu i-aș pune ca dirigintă
I wouldn't put the responsability only on him
008 pe toți să facă treaba asta.
I would have all of them do this task

This discourse brings to the surface at least three elements: (1) the assumption that none of the classmates want to share a desk with the student who is experiencing social anxiety; (2) the idea that the girls—referred to as “the young ladies”—would be more willing than the boys to sit with the student who is experiencing social anxiety; and (3) the expectation that the student with anxiety must make efforts in order to become an active participant in the class community.

Fig. 7 Representation of delivery of group work results

The disagreement expressed in lines 7–8 suggests the need to develop training that specifically addresses teachers’ awareness of the moments when they need to seek help in managing a situation. Kumashiro argues that “the assumption that educators can accurately assess their students’ needs” (Kumashiro 2000, p. 31) is often incorrect.

Suggested classroom activities: challenges

For example, one of the “energizer” exercises during the ICD Congress week involved drawing a house with rounded walls (Fig. 8), and one participant’s feedback was that it was “a bit absurd.” Simple exercises like this make stereotyping mechanisms visible (e.g., the assumption that all houses must have straight edges) and help in overcoming or transforming them. Garfinkel (1967) introduced the concept of the “breaching experiment,” which challenges individuals to behave “strangely” in a context that is familiar to everyone—in other words, to do something that goes against the established social order or rules. For instance, suggesting to a shop assistant that you would like to pay more than the listed price for a product. Such social order becomes visible precisely when it is disrupted.

Fig. 8 Drawings of houses with rounded walls created during the ICD Congress (July 2024)

Context: developing democratic and civic competences in Romanian schools

Efforts to develop democratic and civic competences in Romanian schools over the past two years are visible at the national level (the Ministry of Education), at the level of universities, and, not least, within non-profit organizations.

In 2024, the Ministry of Education published the results of the ICCS evaluation (International Civic and Citizenship Education Study, National Report 2024), based on data from 24 participating countries, including Romania, which took part for the first time. Internationally, approximately 82,000 eighth-grade students and 40,000 teachers who taught regular school subjects to the target grade participated in the study.

The research was carried out in 2022 by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA), and in Romania it was conducted for the Ministry of Education by the University of Bucharest (National Report 2024), involving 158 schools, 2,768 students, and 2,242 teachers and school leaders (National Report 2024).

The main findings focus on the following themes:

Civic knowledge and thinking, civic engagement in school and community, trust in state institutions, voting intentions and participation, and European citizenship.

Regarding civic knowledge and civic thinking, the results of Romanian students are below the ICCS 2022 average:

“Romanian students obtained an average score of 470 on the civic knowledge and thinking assessment, significantly lower than the ICCS 2022 average (508), placing Romania 16th out of the 20 participating countries.

Approximately one quarter of Romanian students are at competence level D or below (compared to 14.2% in the ICCS 2022 average), and about one fifth are at level A (compared to 30.6% in the ICCS 2022 average)” (National Report 2024, our translation).

Beyond students’ perceptions, the report also captures teachers’ perceptions of the context of civic and citizenship education in the schools where they teach. The results show that while 48% of teachers feel “very well prepared” to teach about citizens’ rights and responsibilities, only 31% report feeling equally prepared to teach about diversity and inclusion (National Report 2024).

Another conclusion is that when teachers do not receive initial or ongoing training in inquiry-based, problem-based, project-based, or role-play learning and teaching, it is unlikely that they will offer students opportunities to initiate topics or forms of interaction that they themselves prefer:

„Although teachers report that they give students the opportunity to discuss social and political issues, this tends to occur without allowing students to propose topics, work in teams, or gather information from the community. Moreover, a significant percentage of teachers state that they have not received initial or ongoing training in inquiry-based, problem-based, project-based, or role-play teaching and learning” (National Report 2024, our translation).

Studiul propune 5 recomandări principale pentru școli:

„Promoting the importance of civic and citizenship education among students, teachers, and families;

Aprecierea profesorilor care creează contexte pentru formarea și consolidarea cunoștințelor și gândirii civice;

Recognizing and valuing teachers who create contexts for developing and strengthening civic knowledge and civic thinking;

Recognizing and rewarding students and teachers who are involved in volunteer activities or community service projects;

Encouraging a democratic and inclusive organizational culture at the school level”.
(National Report 2024, our translation)

Students' learning opportunities, teachers' level of preparedness, and their participation in training programs were also explored at the university level by Bădescu et al. (2024) in the study “Civic Education in Romania.” Bădescu and colleagues conducted a study using a complex methodology (interviews, classroom observations, official statistical data, and a survey) involving 940 teachers from across the country who teach Social Education, a subject taught throughout the entire lower-secondary cycle.

The study examines (i) how education for democracy is implemented in Romanian schools, and (ii) describes the profile of teachers who teach Social Education in Romania. The final section of the study is dedicated to “main policy and intervention recommendations for fostering democratic citizenship within schools” (2024, pp. 53–57).

Bădescu et al. (2024) do not focus solely on the content being taught; they also highlight the importance of the classroom climate, teaching methods, and teachers' qualifications, as well as the extent to which teachers uphold democratic values and norms (pp. 3–4).

We note here two of the recommendations included in this final section:

the need for “substantial training” for teachers in Romania regarding competences for democratic culture;

and the need to develop “aspects related to strengthening teachers’ collaboration skills, as well as their knowledge of how to teach in ways that foster collaborative skills among students” (Bădescu et al. 2024, p. 56, our translation).

Regarding training for teaching democratic citizenship education, the results indicate a greater need among teachers who have been teaching Social Education for less than five years (50%) compared to their more experienced colleagues (41%) (Bădescu et al. 2024, pp. 43–44).

Teachers prefer that training activities be organized in the form of communities of practice (48%, Bădescu et al. 2024, Table 11, p. 44), and the authors suggest that “the collaborative dimension of these communities may be decisive in choosing this format” (Bădescu et al. 2024, p. 45, our translation).

At the level of non-profit organizations, in September 2023, Școala de Valori, the Intercultural Institute of Timișoara, and the Techsoup Association joined forces to address the limited capacity of the Romanian education system to develop students’ and teachers’ democratic, civic, and digital competences through the project ICD. ICD is a three-year initiative funded by Fondation Botnar. The project builds on partnerships with 38 schools across the country currently involved in the program and includes a qualitative research component that forms the basis of this publication.

The ICD project carried out an exploratory qualitative analysis of 28 hours of audio-video recordings of interactions among 60 teachers participating in the July 2024 ICD Congress. This publication presents several initial findings focused on the resources, actions, and interactions that contribute to building a democratic school. Recalling the preference expressed by Social Education teachers (Bădescu et al., 2024) for organizing activities as communities of practice, we also included in the final chapter examples of activities implemented by teachers in the ICD community.

Damiani et al. (2024, p. 11) and Bădescu et al. (2024) emphasize that civic citizenship education is the responsibility of all teachers and is not limited to Social Education teachers. While the ICCS study uses questionnaires to collect students’ and teachers’ perceptions, and Bădescu et al. (2024) employ a complex methodology (interviews, classroom observations, official statistical data, and a survey), the ICD exploratory qualitative analysis takes a step beyond perceptions by examining actual interactions with and among teachers.

Activities Implemented by Teachers from the ICD Community

This final section presents examples shared during the monthly community meetings by the teachers participating in the ICD project. Each example includes in parentheses the type of primary practice involved (connecting practices, observation practices, response practices, or practices of recognizing needs).

Example "Carousel" (connexion practices)

Its objective is to help group members get to know one another better and to encourage interaction among children who usually do not interact very much with each other. I divide the students into two groups, usually of equal size. The two groups arrange themselves in concentric circles, one inside the other, with each child having a partner. Within a limited amount of time—30 seconds, one minute, sometimes even two minutes—I say a word or a sentence, and they must find something they have in common. For example, if I say “favorite food,” they must discover what favorite food they share. When I say stop, the outer circle rotates and each child gets a new partner. When the activity ends, I invite them to recall what they discovered they had in common (something they like or dislike).

Example "Keep the rhythm with me" (response practices)

I managed to teach them to keep the rhythm by doing body percussion exercises. Then I invite each of them to come to the front, and each one becomes the teacher for a moment. They all want to come to the front of the class, and even though some of them make mistakes, the others are understanding—they simply point it out without saying anything unkind. They just say it nicely: “It should be like this, and you did it like this.” And they enjoy it.

Example „Discover history with me” (connexion practices)

Last school year, (...) I managed to prepare high school students to go and teach history to lower-secondary students, and they enjoyed it very much, because they interacted especially with younger students. What was very interesting was that after they taught these lessons, the younger students would go and hug them during breaks, greet them—so in a way, a real connection had formed between them.

Example „BINGO” (connexion practices)

The little “BINGO” game I’m proposing now works very well for 2nd- and 3rd-grade classes, when they can write more confidently. It involves giving them sheets with specific questions, and they have to go around and ask each other to find the people who match the prompts: for example, if someone has siblings, they must write down the names of classmates who have a brother or a sister. Or someone who practices a certain sport, or who has read a particular book. Once they had filled in the entire page with classmates’ names, they would shout BINGO. Then we would see whom they had the chance to interact with, whom they asked questions, and what new things they learned about their classmates or friends. It’s a very good method for getting to know each other and discovering things that are less known: what they ate, what sport they like, what passions they share, or whether they can find someone else who has a younger sibling of the same age. With younger children it’s harder, because they cannot write. But they can raise their hands. So I ask the questions, they raise their hands, and they check the boxes on their sheet—each question is represented with a drawing. It’s fun, they get to know each other, and it’s useful.

Example „(anti)democratic element” (practices of recognition of students’ needs)

“An anti-democratic aspect in high school could be the lack of school trips, because we would love to travel together with our teachers and classmates. And a democratic aspect is the teachers, who behave very nicely and teach us good things” (Student).

Fig. 9 Data collected in the classroom, example provided by a participating teacher

Example „Presence” (connexion practices)

I always do the spatial orientation exercise. The purpose of this activity is to see whether the students are fully present. They first draw a tree, then add elements to it, some of them humorous (for example, a jaguar on the right side of the tree). They usually join the activity willingly and wait for additional challenges.

Example „Guess the word” (observation practices)

Slips of paper are prepared with different concepts from the lessons. The students are grouped, and each member must present or explain the word written on their slip, while the other members of the group have to guess which word they have. The time allowed for guessing each word/concept is 1 minute.

Example „Energizer 1” (connexion practices)

Energizer games:

1. I stretched a piece of string across the classroom. They positioned themselves randomly along it, and then I asked them to arrange themselves in ascending order without speaking, based on age or birth date.
2. I encode the lesson title, and the students have to decode it—using Caesar’s cipher, another language, etc.

Example „Energizer 2” (connexion practices)

Sometimes, when I feel that the students are bored, tired, or too noisy, I stop the lesson and start asking questions such as:

- “Stand up if you’re wearing a watch” (then they sit back down);
- “Stand up if you have something black in your outfit”;
- “Stand up if you were born in March,” etc.

The questions vary depending on my creativity in that moment or on how I adapt them to the class and the situation.

Example „Energizer 3” (connexion practices)

We place an object between two students. The teacher says words that name parts of the body, and the students touch the corresponding body part they hear. When they hear a word from the lesson being taught, they must grab the object placed between them.

Example „Transdisciplinary lesson” (observation practices)

I think I want to invite the history teacher to work together on a transdisciplinary lesson (11th grade).

Example „I know about...” (connexion practices)

During the “Morning Meeting” in the preparatory class, I announce the theme. The students, seated in a circle, have the opportunity to share a curiosity or an interesting fact about the announced topic.

Each sentence begins with: “I know about...”

We thank all the teachers for the examples they shared, including (in random order and based on the information available to us):

teacher Sîngeorzan Aurica (Liviu Rebreanu National College, Bistrița),

teacher Irina Aldea (General School No. 49, Bucharest),

teacher Mihaiela Curca (Elena Caragiani Technological High School, Tecuci),

teacher Florina Vișan (Băneasa Theoretical High School),

teacher Ancuța Lung (College of Arts, Baia Mare),

teacher Ionela Tutu,

teacher Angela Pestrițu,

teacher Aurora Olaru,

teacher Elena Minea (Elie Radu Technological Energy High School, Ploiești).

Methodology: interaction analysis

The interactions recorded during the ICD Congress (July 2024) are the subject of an interaction analysis (Mondada 2001, Traverso 2016), a current “that has been developed within the field of conversation analysis” (Traverso 2016, p. 13), drawing on conversation analysis with an ethnomethodological orientation.

We present three principles of interaction analysis:

(1) Conversation/interaction is “a basic form of social organization [...] a process that unfolds as participants exchange verbal utterances/statements [...] a joint construction by the participants” (Gülich 1991, p. 331), as illustrated in Example 2, lines 8–10 and 11.

(2) During a conversation, people generally take turns speaking (Sacks, Schegloff & Jefferson 1974, p. 700); therefore, a conversation involves continuous negotiation of turn allocation, as shown in Example 2. A speech act/utterance “is not a grammatical unit like a sentence, but an interactive unit” (Bange 1992, p. 32), which ends “when the speaking turns shift from one speaker to another” (Traverso 2016, p. 39). At times, speakers overlap, negotiating who will continue the conversation.

(3) The adjacency pair or sequence is the basic unit of analysis, an example being the question–answer pair (Example 2, lines 1–2). The adjacency pair is based on the principle of “adjacency or contiguity” (Schegloff 2007, p. 14). This relationship forms the foundation of conversation analysis, understood as the “arrangement/matching/contact [Fr. agencement] of the activities that participants develop within a given context, where they must adapt their actions to one another” (Bange 1992, p. 18).

Natural conversation (i.e., not experimentally produced) is represented in writing by transcribing all elements of speech. In addition to words, the transcription includes notations (Selting et al. 1998) concerning pauses, pause length, intonation, overlapping talk, etc., as illustrated in Fig. 10.

(.)	micropause
(-), (--), (---)	short, medium, long pause
a:	sound lengthening
,	rising intonation
?	rising intonation with register shift
.	falling intonation
<<reads>>xx>>	comment applying to the text in parentheses
(...)	interaction that was not transcribed
()	unintelligible
[beginning of overlapping speech
]	end of overlapping speech

COURIER NEW this font is used because each character occupies the same space

Fig. 10 Transcription conventions

Conclusions: practices of the teaching community and pedagogical practices for the democratic school

The publication “Școala de Valori: The Democratic School” joins the broader efforts to promote democratic culture and civic citizenship in schools. We have highlighted concerns related to this topic at the European and national levels (Council of Europe 2018, Damiani et al. 2024), at the university level (Bădescu et al. 2024), and then introduced the ICD project, a joint initiative of Școala de Valori, the Intercultural Institute of Timișoara, and the Techsoup Association.

This publication presents several findings from an exploratory qualitative analysis of data collected during the in-person meeting with 60 teachers at the ICD Congress held in Brașov in July 2024. Specifically, it focuses on practices of the teaching community and pedagogical practices which—at the level of teacher–student, student–student, and teacher–teacher interactions—can serve as examples of “interventions for developing democratic citizenship in the school environment” (Bădescu et al., 2024, pp. 53–57): connecting practices, observation practices, response practices, and practices of recognizing needs. Each section also included concrete classroom implementation examples, later complemented by examples contributed by primary, lower-secondary, and high-school teachers in the ICD community.

Through practices such as “Keep the rhythm with me!”, “Discover history with me!”, “Guess the word!”, students act and interact from the position of experts (Moore & Simon 2002, p. 2), within an expanded “learning territory” (Py 2000, p. 2), and with greater “control over classroom discourse” (Moore & Simon 2002, p. 8). Practices of recognizing and acknowledging needs—such as “(Anti)democratic element”—contribute to building a whole-school approach (Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture, 2018), in which students propose initiatives they consider meaningful. Observation practices like “Transdisciplinary lesson” are examples of collaboration (Bădescu et al., 2024) within the teaching community, while energizer practices exemplify collaboration and connection within student or teacher groups.

The exploratory analysis initiated within the ICD project continues in the publications “Școala de Valori – The Innovative School” and “Școala de Valori – The Digital School.” The research process is ongoing, with data collection and analysis currently underway for Years II (2024–2025) and III (2025–2026) of the ICD project.

About The School of Values

The School of Values is a non-governmental and non-profit organization, founded in 2010, that offers young people and teachers in pre-university and university settings experiences that emphasize identifying individual potential, developing life skills, and strengthening the ability to work collaboratively, across disciplines and across generations in order to

to transform today's society into one centered on healthy values. Between 2010 and 2024, Școala de Valori reached, through its projects, 203,997 young people and 12,902 teachers from 6,791 educational institutions across 1,512 localities in Romania. To these figures we add the participants from 2024, as well as the trainers trained by Școala de Valori—164 in 2023 alone.

The educational content, as well as impact research, is structured around six key competences, which describe how these competences are developed and evolve as the beneficiaries of Școala de Valori programs progress in their learning. These six key competences are those that our participants need in order to identify their potential, grow personally, fulfill their aspirations, and achieve personal success, as well as to become innovative entrepreneurs or to secure employment aligned with their interests, to ensure school/social inclusion, and to plan a sustainable lifestyle characterized by well-being and vision within peaceful societies:

- Personal, Social, and Learning-to-Learn Competences
- Active Citizenship, Social Responsibility, and Democratic Culture Competences
- Entrepreneurial and Intrapreneurial Competences
- Cultural Awareness and Expression Competences
- Science, Technology, and Engineering Competences
- Digital Competences

Școala de Valori supports values-based, lifelong learning. When surrounded by others, young people can learn to identify lifelong learning models driven by dedication and curiosity. In other words, values-centered continuous learning enables young people to understand how to learn actively from parents, teachers, inspiring people, influencers, instructors—essentially from anyone they interact with throughout their lives.

Our mission:

„We guide young people to learn to become the creators of their own lives.”

The Team

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Editors:

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About the initiative iCercetare/iResearch

The iCercetare initiative was created within Școala de Valori in 2024 out of the need to document and analyze both the context in which the projects it implements are born and the diversity of their impact at the level of:

- values: values-based education
- development of the six key competences: life skills
- learning as a social process: learning through interaction
- trainer development: training the teams of trainers involved in project implementation
- teacher development: education for democratic competences and digital citizenship
- career guidance
- guiding students in developing social entrepreneurship projects
- guiding teachers and trainers in developing research competences

By the “i” in “iCercetare”, we understand ideas and initiatives in interaction: interaction with field actors (trainers and teachers), with beneficiary groups (students and university students), with professionals who share their experience, and, not least, with European, national, and university-level initiatives.

iCercetare starts from the field and brings research results back into the field in various formats: presentations during community meetings, dissemination publications, training workshops, or—in a pilot format—within focus groups in which teachers are positioned as partners in the research process.

Despre Incubatorul Civic Digital

The Digital Civic Incubator is a digital citizenship project created and implemented by a consortium of three non-governmental organizations—The School of Values, the Intercultural Institute of Timișoara, and the Techsoup Association—with the support of the Ministry of Education. The project is funded by Fondation Botnar.

The project supports education for democratic competences and digital citizenship by providing free professional training to 4,500 teachers and primary school educators, Social Education teachers, ICT and Computer Science teachers, among others, and by implementing transformative interventions in 45 schools.

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Abrevieri

DC - Competences for Democratic Culture

*DCD - Democratic Culture and Democracy

Fig. - Figure

r. - line of text in the example

Fig. 1 Adapted model by Silvia Bogdan, based on the Innovative Digital School Model (Ilomäki & Lakkala 2018).

Fig. 2 Energizer representation, illustration by Guillaume Reynard

Fig. 3 Energizer with a group of teachers participating in the ICD Congress, July 2024

Fig. 4 Representation of a discussion circle, illustration by Guillaume Reynard

Fig. 5 Discussion circle, ICD Congress, July 2024

Fig. 6 Representation of frontal interaction, illustration by Guillaume Reynard

Fig. 7 Representation of delivery of group work results, illustration by Guillaume Reynard

Fig. 8 Drawings of houses with rounded walls created during the ICD Congress (July 2024)

Fig. 9 Data collected in the classroom, example provided by a participating teacher

Fig. 10 Transcription conventions

iCercetare

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